

The High-Degree Gravity (g)-modes Sequences in HD 4539

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HD 4539

HD 4539 is a well known, bright ($V=10.24$ mag), subdwarf-B (sdB) star for which g-mode pulsations have been suspected but not confirmed [5, 3]. From observations made by the Kepler spacecraft we confirm HD 4539 (=EPIC 220641886) to be a long-period V1093 Her-type pulsating sdB star. The full K2 data set spans ~ 80 days, and from this we extract 153 significant pulsation frequencies. K2 dataset had revealed that HD 4539 is a hybrid pulsator sdB giving it a rich asteroseismic potential. The amplitude spectrum of the star displays a rich content of gravity (g)-modes. The low-frequency region ($<2000 \mu\text{Hz}$) includes at least 144 independent g-modes, while the high frequency region ($>2000 \mu\text{Hz}$) consists of only 9 pressure p-modes. We used asymptotic period spacing to identify the modal degree of the majority of the modes, ranging from $l=1$ to $l=12$, apart from $l=3$ and $l=11$ modes, that are not seen. For the first time in a subdwarf B pulsator, the identification of the modes seems quite robust up to $l=6$.

Rotational Multiplets

In the presence of stellar rotation, non-radial modes of degree l split into $2l+1$ components differing in azimuthal (m) number. In the case of slow rotation, the frequency splitting can be derived from the following equation

$$\nu_{n,l,m} = \nu_{n,l,0} + \Delta\nu_{n,l,m} = \nu_{n,l,0} + m \frac{1 - C_{n,l}}{P_{\text{rot}}} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\nu_{n,l,m}$ is a rotational splitting. P_{rot} is a star's rotation period and $C_{n,l}$ is the Ledoux constant [2]. We searched for multiplets in the entire range of the amplitude spectra, however we did not find any of them. The absence of multiplets due to the frequency splitting suggests that the star is either pole-on oriented or that it has a very long rotation period. Both g- and p-mode regions display complex patterns due to either short observing run or non-linear mode interactions which makes them elusive.

The Sliding Fourier Transform of HD 4539

Although K2 data set is significantly shorter than the Kepler nominal data set, we have looked at the stability of the oscillation modes in HD 4539 via the sliding Fourier Transform. We show three different regions of frequencies. In the following plots we see that both the pulsation frequencies and amplitudes of some modes show small variations in time. This is most likely indicating rotational beating with a period well above 80 days.

Asymptotic Period Spacing

In order to identify the pulsation modes in the g-mode region, we used asymptotic period spacing. In the asymptotic limit ($n \gg l$), consecutive radial overtones are evenly spaced in period [1]. For given n and l values, periods of consecutive overtones can be derived from the following equation,

$$\Pi_{l,n} = \frac{\Pi_0}{\sqrt{l(l+1)}} n + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

where $\Pi_{l,n}$ is the period spacing, Π_0 and ϵ are constants [4]. It has been determined that the dipole ($l=1$) period spacings for sdB stars are ~ 250 s [4] and for HD 4539 the average of the period spacing for the dipole modes is $\Pi_{l=1} = 256.5$ s. Using the ratio between the modes we searched for the potential sequences in the period domain. We have found 10 sequences between $l=1$ and $l=12$, excluding $l=3$ and $l=11$ which are not seen, likely due to cancellation effects. Since the period spacing changes with l (gets lower with increasing l), the identification of the modes seems quite robust, at least up to $l=6$, as can be seen in the échelle diagrams below.

Échelle Diagrams

We have produced the échelle diagrams for $1 \leq l \leq 12$ and all diagrams show deviations from the period modulo (average period spacing). Here, we have shown the échelle diagrams for $1 \leq l \leq 7$ with the exception of $l=3$.

Conclusion

We have analysed K2 observations of one of the brightest known sdBs, confirming that HD 4539 is a V1093 Her-type pulsator, and identifying more than 150 pulsation frequencies (144 g-modes, 9 p-modes). Using asymptotic relations, we have identified sequences of near-consecutive modes for degrees (l) ($1 \leq l \leq 12$) which will be crucial to make a realistic asteroseismic models of the star. The modes can be seen also in the échelle diagrams with their characteristic shapes that were found in many Kepler subdwarf B pulsators [6].

References

- [1] S. Charpinet, G. Fontaine, P. Brassard, and B. Dorman. Adiabatic Survey of Subdwarf B Star Oscillations. I. Pulsation Properties of a Representative Evolutionary Model. *ApJS*, 131:223–247, November 2000.
- [2] P. Ledoux. The Nonradial Oscillations of Gaseous Stars and the Problem of Beta Canis Majoris. *ApJ*, 114:373, November 1951.
- [3] A. E. Lynas-Gray. Photometric Variability of HD 4539? In D. Kilkenny, C. S. Jeffery, and C. Koen, editors, *Fifth Meeting on Hot Subdwarf Stars and Related Objects*, volume 452 of *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*, page 213, March 2012.
- [4] M. D. Reed, A. Baran, A. C. Quint, S. D. Kawaler, S. J. O'Toole, J. Telting, S. Charpinet, C. Rodríguez-López, R. H. Østensen, J. L. Provencal, E. S. Johnson, S. E. Thompson, C. Allen, C. K. Middour, H. Kjeldsen, and J. Christensen-Dalsgaard. First Kepler results on compact pulsators - VIII. Mode identifications via period spacings in g-mode pulsating subdwarf B stars. *MNRAS*, 414:2885–2892, July 2011.
- [5] C. Schoenaers and A. E. Lynas-Gray. A new slowly pulsating subdwarf-B star: HD 4539. *Communications in Asteroseismology*, 151:67–76, August 2007.
- [6] J. H. Telting, R. H. Østensen, A. S. Baran, S. Bloemen, M. D. Reed, R. Oreiro, L. Farris, T. A. Ottosen, C. Aerts, S. D. Kawaler, U. Heber, S. Prins, E. M. Green, B. Kalomeni, S. J. O'Toole, F. Mullally, D. T. Sanderfer, J. C. Smith, and H. Kjeldsen. Three ways to solve the orbit of KIC 11 558 725: a 10-day beaming sdB+WD binary with a pulsating subdwarf. *A&A*, 544:A1, August 2012.